

A light-trap survey of the abundance and sex ratio of leafhoppers and planthoppers in Egypt

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Leafhoppers and planthoppers were surveyed in rice fields at Kafr-el-Sheikh, northern Egypt, with a light trap operated 2 nights/week throughout 1974–1975. Twelve species of the Cicadellidae family, six of Delphacidae, and one species each of Cixiidae and Meenoplidae families were trapped. Considerably more insects were caught in 1975 than in 1974 — 129.4 vs 83.2 Cicadellidae/night and 134.6 vs 121.2

Delphacidae/night. The highest monthly averages were in June and July for *Empoasca decipiens* and *Macrosteles sexnotatus*; August and September for *Balclutha hortensis*, *Cicadulina bipunctella zaeae*, *Exitianus taeniaticeps*, *Balclutha rufofasciata*, *Neolimninus aegyptiacus*, and *Orosius albicinctus*; and October for *Nephotettix modulatus* and *Recilia schmidtgeni*. The monthly averages for delphacids were highest in September and October.

The sex ratio in the light-trap catches was near equality (44–54% males) in *N. aegyptiacus*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Falctoya aglauros*, *Matutinus iphias*, *Perkinsiella insignis*, and *Oliarus frontalis*. But males were more prominent (57–70%) in *E. taeniaticeps*, *Sogatella vibix*, and *Nisia atrovonosa*. The male catch was much lower (< 40%) in the other species.

The relative abundance and sex ratio of leafhoppers and planthoppers caught in lit trap in rice fields, Kafr-el Sheikh, Egypt, 1974–75.

Family and species	Av. no./night		Peak no./night ^a		Females (av. %) 1974–75
	1974	1975	1974	1975	
<i>Family Cicadellidae</i>					
<i>Balclutha hortensis</i>	40.5	50.6	308.3	258.6	37.6
<i>Cicadulina bipunctella zaeae</i>	20.0	36.2	162.3	176.8	34.8
<i>Empoasca decipiens</i>	12.3	30.1	83.3	211.8	23.5
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i>	6.4	6.6	38.9	46.6	30.2
<i>Macrosteles sexnotatus</i>	1.2	3.1	5.7	21.9	20.0
<i>Exitianus taeniaticeps</i>	1.4	1.6	3.4	6.8	57.3
<i>Recilia schmidtgeni</i>	0.8	0.6	5.0	2.4	34.2
<i>Balclutha rufofasciata</i>	0.3	0.3	1.3	1.3	39.7
<i>Neolimninus aegyptiacus</i>	0.2	0.2	1.0	0.9	43.8
<i>Orosius albicinctus</i>	0.1	0.0	1.0	0.4	14.3
<i>Batrachomorphus signatus</i>	0.0	0.1	0.4	0.7	—
<i>Neolaliturus haematoceps</i>	0.0	0.01	0.0	0.1	—
Total	83.2	129.4	522.7	457.0	—
<i>Family Delphacidae</i>					
<i>Sogatella vibix</i>	108.7	120.7	1,009.1	908.0	64.8
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	6.1	7.2	37.1	41.1	53.8
<i>Toya nigeriensis</i>	3.3	3.0	22.1	20.1	38.7
<i>Falctoya aglauros</i>	2.4	2.9	17.5	22.2	49.5
<i>Matutinus iphias</i>	0.4	0.5	2.2	3.7	54.4
<i>Perkinsiella insignis</i>	0.3	0.3	1.6	2.1	46.7
Total	121.2	134.6	1,088.5	997.2	—
<i>Family Cixiidae</i>					
<i>Oliarus frontalis</i>	0.7	0.5	2.9	2.7	51.6
<i>Family Meenoplidae</i>					
<i>Nisia atrovonosa</i>	0.2	0.2	1.1	0.8	70.2

^aMonthly average.

Ovicidal activity of insecticides for brown planthopper control

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* injects its eggs into the tissues of rice leaf sheaths, making contact with insecticides difficult. Because most insecticides have short residual activity, control of the nymphs that hatch a few days after application is poor. Such nymphs may increase BPH populations after spraying. Consequently, the proper timing of insecticide application is of utmost importance. But before growers can achieve it, they must be trained to monitor BPH populations. Application timing would be less critical if insecticides that act as ovicides (i.e. that cause egg mortality) as well as kill BPH nymphs and adults are used.

The ovicidal activity of several insecticides commonly used for rice pest control was studied at IRRI. BPH were allowed to oviposit on plants for 24 hours. At 1 day after oviposition the plants were sprayed with a 0.04% concentration of the insecticides BPMC,

Comparative hatchability of brown planthopper eggs at different ages when different concentrations of carbofuran are used. IRRI, 1976.